

Station: Manufacturing H₂O

≙ 1000 liter H₂O

Select your scenario!

from **A** (H₂O -low)
to **D** (H₂O -high)

Guiding questions:

The guiding questions help you gradually understand the differences between the scenarios and maintain an overview.

No
blocks

A

B

C

D

My smartphone is ...

... received
from relatives.

... second-hand
purchased.

... a Fairphone.

... new
purchased.

The smartphone is ... old.

... > 3 years

... 3 years

... 1-2 years

... < 1 year

I use the device ...

... a few times
per week.

... < 1 hour per
day.

... 1-3 hours per
day.

... > 3 hours per
day.

When the device is no longer
needed, I will ...

... pass it on.

... dispose it
properly /
recycle it.

... put it away.

... throw it
away.